

IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF INNOVATION PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7807686>

Abstract: a methodology for assessing the management of innovation processes in the field of ICT has been developed and an analysis has been carried out taking into account the direct relationship of ICT development to the effectiveness of innovation process management in this area. The forecast indicators were calculated based on the method of assessing the management of innovation processes in the field of ICT.

Keywords: innovation processes, real sector, management, electronic business, Internet, information technologies.

Today, among the innovative processes in the ICT sector, it is possible to include: the emergence of mobile communication and the Internet; the development of mobile Internet; the development of mobile applications; the creation of cloud technologies; the development of e-commerce and e - business; the development of 3G and 4G mobile Internet; the introduction of Wi-Fi technologies; the mass introduction of intellectual platform services; IoT - (Internet of Things) Internet of things.

In recent years, there have been a number of methods in world experience that assess the development of innovation in countries, in which the development of the ICT sector is important. In the management of innovation processes in the ICT sector, the indicators contained in international indices are evaluated by determining the integral indicator and comparing it with the share of the ICT Sox in GDP. The data obtained from the management of innovation processes in the ICT sector based on the indicators of the global index on cyber security, the level of preparation for e-commerce, global innovation development and the level of development of ICT. At this point, it should be noted that each of the listed indices covers the development of ICT innovation in the country to some extent, and as a result, in these ratings, the ICT sector of the country reflects the effectiveness of management of innovation processes. With the study of these indices, indicators were formed by the author assessing the effectiveness of innovative process management in the ICT field, and an assessment methodology was proposed.

We can know the management of innovative processes in our country by evaluating the results of innovative activities. In the previous section, we examined the evaluation of innovational activities through indices and ratings on the jaxon scale. Innovation activity in our republic is achieved through a number of indicators. In ICT, however, the dynamics of development of ICT infrastructure can be cited as a result of innovation process management (Table 1).

Table 1.

Development of ICT infrastructure in Uzbekistan¹

¹ Based on the data of the Ministry of development of information technologies and communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Nº	Specification name	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	mobile coverage	45	70	86	96%	98%
2	broadband coverage of mobile communications	23	44	58	70%	72%
3	number of mobile users	20,6	21,4	22,8	29,8	31
4	Number of internet service users	17	18	20	25	27
5	number of mobile internet users	11	14	21	27	29

In the ICT sector, innovation is evaluated in process management by determining the integral indicator of the indicators contained in international indices and comparing it with the share of the ICT Sox in GDP. It should be noted that on a global scale there is no perfect index that reflects the management of innovative processes of the country's particular ICT sector, one of the reasons for which is the fact that constantly newly introduced technologies are evaluated by new criteria, and it is reflected in the fact that it is derived from specific characteristics in different countries.

Figure 1. Methodology for assessing the effectiveness of innovative process management in the field of Information Communication Technologies in Uzbekistan²

The data obtained from the management of innovation processes in the ICT sector based on the indicators of the global index on cyber security, the level of preparation for e-commerce, global innovation development and the level of development of ICT. At this point, it should be noted that each of the listed indices covers the development of ICT innovation in the country to some extent, and as a result, in these ratings, the ICT sector of the country reflects the effectiveness of management of innovation processes. With the study of these indices, indicators were formed by the author assessing the effectiveness of innovative process management in the ICT field, and an assessment methodology was proposed.

As for the results of 2021, the coverage of mobile communication reached 98%, while the wide-line coverage of mobile communication shows 72%. The number of internet users has also exceeded 29 million today, despite the decline in the growth rate in recent years (Table 2).

Table 2
ICT industry innovation processes forecast indicators on management performance assessment methodology³

Nº	Specification name	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2030
1.	Innovation communication indicators	12	14,7	15,5	18,5	20	22
2.	Indicators of human capital involved in innovation processes	7,5	7,5	8	9	15	23
3.	Digital business indicators	7	11	13	15	15	20
4.	Innovation goods and services indicators	5,5	7,5	9	14	16	22
5.	Integral indicator	35	40,7	45,5	56,5	66	87

Based on the forecast indicators, the integral indicator in 2030 is 87 points, which indicates an increase of 2.5 times compared to the current state.

"Uzbektelecom" AK innovation process management sets out the directions for achieving their future efficiency:

- mastering new technologies. Transport networks, network ownership and leadership in information technology infrastructure.
- innovation development of products and services. A unified content management system: cloud technologies, distributed infrastructure services and other similar modern services.
- innovations in management. Increase competitiveness in the Global market and reduce large amounts of costs.
- energy efficiency and ecology. Leadership and high social responsibility in cost management.

The innovation development strategy of the uzbektelecom stock company is instrumental in developing a corporate management system based on a set of interconnected methodological and scientific and practical rules for managing innovation processes, making changes to the organizational structure of the company in order to adapt organizational structures to market conditions, and developing a long-term innovation development roadmap.

² Developed by the author.

³ Developed by the author

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